

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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METHODS AND EXAMPLES OF TRANSLATING WHILE PRESERVING THE ORIGINAL SPEECH OF A CHARACTER

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Abstract. *Maintaining the originality of a character's speech in translation is essential for preserving their identity, personality, and cultural nuances. Even though modern translation schools are representing high professionalism on saving the originality of the literature they are releasing, there are still subtle issues to be concerned by researchers assuming to tackle them down. This paper explores key techniques for achieving this balance, including capturing dialects, preserving slang and idioms, conveying character personality, adapting cultural references, retaining wordplay, adjusting for form and syntax, and translating emotional expressions. Supported by linguistic research, this study highlights strategies that ensure authenticity in translated literary works.*

Key words: *emotional expressions, literary translations, character's speech, character personality, idiomatic speech, maintaining originality.*

Introduction. Translating literary works presents a unique challenge: preserving the distinctiveness of a character's speech while ensuring clarity and cultural relevance in the target language. A successful translation must maintain accuracy, readability, and authenticity without stripping away the character's voice. As well-known linguist V. Vinogradov (1967) stated the research of literary fiction language is close to linguistics and literary studies, but each of them should be the object of investigation of a special philological discipline, distinct from the other two. A plethora of factors contribute to saving originality of the translations, as the scholarly analysis of the field behooves a translator meticulously select the approach once a text is being translated from a particular language into another. While translating emotional expressions the categories of emotions across languages (Boster, 2005) is suggested to be taken into consideration. Saving originality of the original text is considered to be high in importance (Sodiqova ,2023; Usmanova, 2009; Asadova, 2023) in the researches of the young linguists over the recent years.

This paper examines strategies used in translation to retain linguistic and cultural features of speech while ensuring accessibility for new audiences. Key theories from Venuti (1995), Baker (2011) , Berman (1985), Nida (1969) , and other scholars will be explored to demonstrate best practices in literary translation.

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Materials and Research Methods. This investigative article employs a number of literary works of well known authors' novels and short stories originally written in English, French and Uzbek languages. These materials are selected to be analyzed and showcase the difference of the character's speech delicate translations, providing a comprehensive basis for discussion of characters speech in literary translation.

The selected materials include:

1. American Literature: Renowned authors such as Mark Twain and J.D. Salinger
2. British Literature: Works from the outstanding XIX century authors such as Arthur Conan Doyle and Lewis Carol, along with modern fantasy writer J.K. Rowling.
3. French Literature: Text from Victor Hugo's masterpiece
4. Uzbek literature: a light hearted novel by Gafur Gulam.

This study is based on a comparative analysis of literary translations, examining the effectiveness of different translation strategies. Several examples of translated dialogue will be presented to illustrate how dialects, slang, idioms, personality, cultural references, wordplay, emotional expressions, and syntax can be effectively maintained. Research from translations of literary texts provides theoretical support for these methods.

The selected comparative approach examines the translated passages to determine how each approach impacts the retention of the original text's style, meaning, and emotional resonance.

This includes:

- a) Word-for-word correctness and the degree to which the original text's structure and meaning are preserved are assessed in a literal translation.
- b) Free translation: Evaluating how well the original work's general tone and sense are conveyed, even if the particular terminology is altered.
- c) Adaptive translation is the process of evaluating how successfully the source material is modified to meet the target audience's cultural background while maintaining its main ideas and visual appeal.

Besides, two-way comparison method in which the source text (ST) and the target text (TT) are both examined at the same time in the author's proposed two-way comparison method. This method helps to counteract the drawbacks of random selection and enables a more thorough understanding of the translation process.

Through the methodical use and comparison of these techniques over a wide range of literary texts, this study seeks to pinpoint optimal practices in literary

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translation and offer recommendations for translators to produce translations of superior quality that honor and conserve the core of the original documents.

Results and Discussion. Capturing Dialects and Regionalisms. Characters often speak in dialects or regional variations that reflect their background. A literal translation may strip away this uniqueness, so translators must find equivalents in the target language. Example from Fiction: In *Mark Twain's The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*, Jim's speech is heavily dialectal: Original: "I doan' want to go no mo'." (Twain, 1885, Chapter 23, p. 3) Standard English: "I don't want to go anymore."

Uzbek Translation: "Men boshqa borishni xohlamayman." (loses dialectal uniqueness) Alternative Uzbek Translation: "Men endi bormayman." (maintains informal, dialectal tone) Preserving Slang and Idioms. Slang and idiomatic expressions often lack direct equivalents, requiring creative adaptation. Example from Fiction: In *J.D. Salinger's The Catcher in the Rye*, Holden Caulfield frequently uses slang: Original: "That kills me." (meaning: that makes me laugh or fascinates me) (Salinger, 1951, p. 125). Uzbek Translation: "Bu meni o'ldiradi." (literal, but doesn't convey the same meaning) . Alternative: "Bu meni rosa kuldiradi." (captures the humor and tone)

Conveying Character Personality and Tone. The way a character speaks reflects their personality—whether they are witty, serious, rude, or sophisticated. A translation should maintain this consistency. Example from Fiction: In *Sherlock Holmes* by Arthur Conan Doyle, Holmes speaks in a formal, precise manner: Original: "The game is afoot." (Doyle, 1892, "The Adventure of the Abbey Grange"). Literal Uzbek translation: "O'yin boshlandi." (awkward, unnatural) Better

Alternative: "Ish boshlanmoqda." (preserves the detective tone) Adapting Cultural References. Cultural references can be problematic, as they may not be familiar to the target audience. Instead of a direct translation, consider replacing them with culturally relevant alternatives.

Retaining Wordplay and Puns. Wordplay and puns are notoriously difficult to translate and often require recreation rather than direct translation. Example from Fiction: In *Lewis Carroll's Alice's Adventures in Wonderland*, there is a pun on "tortoise" and "taught us": Original: "We called him Tortoise because he taught us." (Carroll, 1865, Chapter 9). Literal Uzbek Translation: "Biz uni Toshbaqa deb atadik, chunki u bizga o'rgatdi." (loses the pun) Better Alternative: "Biz uni Talbaqa deb atadik, chunki u bizga ta'lim berdi." (attempts to preserve the wordplay)

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Adjusting for Form and Syntax. Languages have different sentence structures, and sometimes, adjustments are necessary to make speech sound natural while maintaining its original intent.

Translating Emotional Expressions While Keeping Originality. Emotional expressions are deeply tied to cultural and linguistic structures, making their translation particularly challenging. A direct translation may fail to convey the intended intensity, subtlety, or cultural resonance of an emotion. Translators must consider emotional equivalence rather than linguistic accuracy. Example from Fiction: In *Les Misérables* by Victor Hugo, Jean Valjean expresses deep sorrow:

Original (French): “*Mon cœur se brise.*” (Literally: “My heart breaks.”) (Hugo, 1862, Volume 2, Book 5, Chapter 5).\

English translation: “*My heart is breaking.*” (Preserves meaning but lacks poetic weight) Uzbek translation: “*Yuragim sinmoqda.*” (retains literal meaning but sounds unnatural)

Alternative: “*Ichim ezilib ketayapti.*” (more natural and expressive in Uzbek)

Example from Fiction: In *Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone* by J.K. Rowling, Hagrid's emotions are exaggerated:

Original (English): “*I should not have said that.*” (Spoken in regret by Hagrid) (Rowling, 1997, Chapter 5) French translation: “*Je n'aurais pas dû dire ça.*” (Loses his informal tone) Uzbek translation: “*Men buni aytmashligim kerak edi.*” (too formal)

Alternative: “*Bekor aytdim-da.*” (captures Hagrid's casual speech)

Preserving the originality of translations of emotional sentences in a fictional character's speech is essential. For instance, the English translation of the hero's speech in G. Ghulam's "Shum Bola" contains a large number of emotionally charged words. For example, “-Hoy, hoy, nima deyapsan, jinni? – debso‘rab qoldi. In Eenglish Translation: “-Hey, hey, why do you shout like that, you idiot? ” Or one more example, “-Voy, ablah-ey, pochchangning qumrisini nima qilding? -Nima qilibman? -Lo`lilarga sotgan ekansan-ku! -Sotmaganman. Molga ayirbosh qilganman. -Mollaring shumi, boy bo`lib qolibsan, ey lo`livachcha.”

English translation: “-Hey, you, silly, what did you do to your brother-in-law's bird? -What did I do? -You had sold it to a gypsy! -I did not sell it, I exchanged it for something.”

Studies by Katan (2009) in *Translating Cultures* emphasize the importance of cultural context when translating emotions, as different languages conceptualize and express feelings uniquely. A failure to adapt emotional expressions can result in loss of meaning or impact.

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Conclusion. This study demonstrates that translating character speech requires a balance between fidelity to the original and adaptation for the target audience. Key techniques such as dialect preservation, idiomatic adaptation, cultural adjustments, and emotional expression modifications help maintain authenticity while ensuring readability. Research from scholars like Venuti, Baker, Berman, and Nida provides valuable guidance in achieving this balance. Future research could explore how modern AI translation tools handle these complexities and compare their effectiveness to human translators.

Moreover, the aforementioned points demonstrate that scholars have always focused on preserving the originality in the translation of emotive sentences in the hero's speech, elucidating the traits of the attitude toward the language of the work of fiction, and conducting a thorough analysis of it. The reason for this is that without understanding the linguistic elements of the work, it is impossible to fully comprehend the basic idea and content of the fiction when analyzing and combining it. It should be mentioned that numerous scientific research on the translation, language analysis, and study of fictional works have been conducted in the fields of English and Uzbek linguistics as well as international linguistics.

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